

table). Spacings were in the main plot and N treatments in subplots. The soil was a silt loam with pH 8.5, 0.23% organic carbon, 17 kg available P/ha, 86 kg available K/ha, and EC 0.44 mmho/cm at 25°C.

Sixty-day-old Janaki seedlings were transplanted 8 Aug 1981. N was applied as urea. PK at 8.6 and 8.3 kg/ha as a single superphosphate and muriate of potash were applied at puddling. The crop was harvested 7 Dec 1981 from a net plot size of 6.25 m² and grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture.

N rate and timing significantly affected grain yield (see table). Maximum grain yield was obtained with 40 kg N/ha applied basally. It was 11 and 9% higher than yield with the same N applied in equal splits at transplanting and panicle initiation, or at transplanting and tillering. Higher yield was due mainly to more panicles/m².

At 20 kg N/ha, basal N application increased yield 10% over the same dose applied at panicle initiation. Poor yield

Grain yield and yieldcontributing characters as affected by different spacing and fertilizer treatments, Pusa, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle weight (g)
Spacing (cm)				
20 × 20	1.7	119	18	2.5
20 × 15	1.9	149	18	2.2
15 × 15	1.9	171	18	2.1
20 × 10	2.0	177	17	2.0
Time and rate (kg/ha) of N application				
Control	1.6	143	18	2.0
20 as basal	1.9	159	18	2.4
20 at panicle initiation (PI)	1.7	149	17	2.1
40 as basal	2.2	171	18	2.3
20 as basal + 20 at PI	2.0	157	17	2.2
20 as basal + 20 at tillering	2.0	145	18	2.6
CD 5% for				
Spacing	ns	20	ns	0.2
Rate and time of N application	0.2	16	0.7	0.2

due to late N application may be associated with lower tiller productivity. These results indicate that time of N application was most critical for the late-transplanted crop.

Although the grain yield was statistically similar at different spacings,

20- × 15-cm spacing appeared to be best, and increased yield 12% over that with 20- × 20-cm spacing. Panicles/m² increased with closer spacing, while panicle weight and percent spikelet fertility decreased. Panicle length and 1,000-grain weight were unaffected by spacing. □

Effect of different levels of N, P, and azolla on rice

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We studied the effect of different levels of N, P, and azolla (*Azolla pinnata* R. Br.) on rice in 1983 kharif. Soil was a sandy clay with pH 6.7, 285.50 kg available N/ha, 26.92 kg available P/ha, and 340.90 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in a split-plot design with nine main plot and three subplot treatments in three replications. Main plot treatments were 0, 50, and 100 kg N/ha as urea and 0, 11, and 22 kg P/ha as single superphosphate. Subplot treatments were no azolla and azolla intercropped or dual-cropped with rice.

In the intercropped plots, 3t azolla/ha was inoculated 1 d after transplanting (DT) rice, grew with rice, and was incorporated twice after transplanting. In dual-cropped plots, 3 t azolla/ha was inoculated at 20 d before transplanting, allowed to grow as a monocrop and an

Table 1. Effect of different levels of N, P, and azolla on yield and yield parameters of rice, Bangalore, India, 1983 kharif.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain to straw ratio	Weight of single panicle (g)	Grain weight per panicle (g)
N (kg/ha)					
0	5.3	5.5	1.0	1.7	1.4
50	5.0	6.7	0.8	1.6	1.3
100	4.7	7.5	0.7	1.5	1.2
CD P: 0.05	ns	0.6	0.1	ns	ns
P (kg/ha)					
0	5.0	6.6	0.8	1.6	1.3
11	5.0	6.4	0.8	1.5	1.3
22	5.0	6.8	0.8	1.6	1.3
CD P: 0.05	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
No azolla					
Intercrop	5.1	5.8	0.9	1.7	1.4
Dual crop	5.2	6.3	0.9	1.7	1.4
	4.7	7.6	0.6	1.3	1.0
CD P: 0.05	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1
CD P: 0.01	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.2

^a ns = not significant.

intercrop, and incorporated twice each, before and after transplanting. N was applied in equal splits at transplanting and 30 DT, P was applied basally, and 42 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied basally to all plots. Jaya was transplanted

at 20- × 10-cm spacing on 18 Jul and harvested 19 Nov 1983.

Applying N and azolla improved rice growth and increased straw yield (Table 1). Grain yield was adversely affected at higher N levels and in dual azolla

cropping because of reduced panicle weight and grain weight/panicle, caused by poor grain filling. This may have been due to overcrowding and mutual shading of plants during the 40 d from transplanting to panicle initiation.

Grain yield was highest (5.8 t/ha) in dual azolla cropping without fertilizer N, followed by that with 50 kg N/ha (Table 2). Results indicated that only a small amount of added N is needed to obtain higher grain yield, and a poorly timed ex-

Table 2. Effect of N and azolla interaction on rice grain yield, Bangalore, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Rice grain yield (t/ha)		
	No azolla	Intercropping	Dual cropping
0	4.9	5.8	5.1
50	5.5	5.0	4.7
100	5.0	4.8	4.2
CD P: 0.05	0.6 ^a		0.7 ^b

^aBetween 2 azolla means at the same level of N. ^bBetween 2 N means at the same or different levels of azolla.

cessive N supply may adversely affect the grain yield where soils have good N and P

status. Applying P did not significantly affect grain yield. □

Effect of N sources and levels on deep water rice

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We studied the effect of N source and level on deep water rice yield at Thot Not in 1983 wet season. Soil was a Sulfaquept with pH 4.5, 0.178% N, 0.067% P₂O₅, 0.067% SO₄²⁻, 2.88 meq Al³⁺/100 g, and 0.56 meq H⁺/100 g. Water depth reached 120 cm in mid-Oct.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with 18-m² subplots and 3 replications. Thirty-five-day-old Nang Tay Dum (local floating variety) and RD19 (modern variety) were transplanted at 25- × 30-cm spacing in the main plots. Prilled urea (PU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), or urea supergranules (USG) were applied at 14.5, 29, or 43.5 kg N/ha and com-

Yield of Nang Tay Dum and RD19 at different N sources^a and levels, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1983.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)										Mean
	0 N	14.5 kg N/ha			29 kg N/ha			43.5 kg N/ha			
		PU	SCU	USG	PU	SCU	USG	PU	SCU	USG	
RD19	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.3	1.7	1.5	1.6	1.9	1.4
Nang Tay Dum	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.6	2.1	1.4
Varieties : ns		CV (%) 21.96									
Nitrogen : LSD 5%: 0.23		CV (%) 13.88									
Variety × nitrogen : ns		CV (%) 13.88									

^aPU = prilled urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranules.

pared to a no-N control. Basal P at 18 kg/ha was applied to all plots.

PU and SCU were broadcast and incorporated 10 d after transplanting (DT) and USG was placed 10 cm deep between 4 hills at 7 DT.

Yield increased with increased N application (see table). At 43.5 kg N/ha, USG performed better than SCU or PU. At 14.5 kg N/ha, yields were similar for all N sources. SCU generally performed

poorly because of the acid sulfate soil.

Varietal performance and interaction between varieties and N management did not significantly differ. Although RD19 has improved plant type, a high percentage of unfilled grains, few grains/panicle, and gall midge damage caused it to yield the same as Nang Tay Dum. Drought at early growth reduced yield of both varieties. □

N release from sesbania green manure and effect of time of application of N fertilizer on lowland rice

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Interest is increasing in the use of organic and green manures for rice culture. At the PAU farm, we showed that N release from sesbania (*Sesbania aculeata*) incorporated in irrigated rice depended on the number of days it was buried before transplanting. Incorporation 1 d before transplanting released 60-120 kg N/ha,

1. Effect of sesbania on KCl-extractable NH₄⁺-N in a flooded soil under laboratory and field conditions, Ludhiana, India.